

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Question
Binge-Watching Behavior (X1)	Time Pattern	Duration	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) I watch micro-dramas for over 30 minutes a day. 2) I can watch over four episodes of a micro-drama without a break.
		Habitual viewing	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Watching micro-dramas has become a habit for me. 2) I often watch micro-dramas without planning ahead.
	Loss of Control	Addiction	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) I have a hard time stopping once I start watching micro-dramas, and I end up finishing the series. 2) I often lose track of time while watching micro-dramas.
		Emotional attachment	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) I find it easy to get caught up in the storyline when watching micro-dramas. 2) I feel like I care about what happens to the characters in the micro-dramas.
In-feed advertising (X2)	Exposure Frequency	Ad appearance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) I often see micro-drama ads pop up on my social media feeds. 2) I often watch micro-dramas all the way through.
	Perceived Ad Value	Personalization	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The micro-drama ads that appeared felt tailored to my viewing preferences. 2) I felt like the micro-drama ads I saw were aligned with my social media activities and habits.
		Entertainment	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The ad features a compelling storyline. 2) The micro-drama ad provides a pleasant viewing experience.
		Informativeness	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Micro-drama ads help me understand the content offered. 2) Micro-drama ads provide useful information to me.
Emotional Appeal (M)	Curiosity	Story-driven	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The micro-drama ad made me curious about the story's continuation. 2) I wanted to know how the story in the micro-drama ad would develop.
	Affective Reaction	Media Enjoyment	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) I felt enthusiastic while watching the micro-drama commercial. 2) I had a pleasant experience while watching the micro-drama commercial.
		Emotional	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) I find my emotions are easily triggered

		Arousal	<p>when watching micro-drama commercials.</p> <p>2) I feel tense or carried away when watching micro-drama commercials.</p>
Subscription Intention (Y)	Conviction	Perceived Benefit	<p>1) I believe that subscribing to a micro-drama streaming app will enhance my viewing experience.</p> <p>2) I believe that subscribing to a micro-drama streaming app can help me get the entertainment I need.</p> <p>3) I believe that subscribing to a micro-drama streaming app can benefit me.</p>
		Ease of use/ efficiency	<p>1) I believe that subscribing to a micro-drama platform makes it easier for me to access the content I want.</p> <p>2) I believe that subscribing to a micro-drama platform makes it more convenient for me to access entertainment.</p>
	Desire	Willingness to subscribe	<p>1) I'm interested in subscribing to a micro-drama streaming platform after watching an advertisement.</p> <p>2) I'm willing to subscribe to a micro-drama streaming platform to enjoy more comprehensive content.</p>
		Continuance desire	<p>1) I want to continue watching the micro-drama story through the platform offered.</p> <p>2) I'm interested in accessing follow-up episodes or exclusive content through the micro-drama streaming platform.</p>